

Supplementary Material to the Pragmatic Verification and Validation of Industrial Executable SysML Models

Description of the Model Transformation Workflows

Benedek Horváth^{*†} Vince Molnár[‡] Bence Graics[‡] Ákos Hajdu[‡] István Ráth^{*}
 Ákos Horváth^{*} Robert Karban[§] Gelys Trancho[¶] Zoltán Micskei[‡]

This report is supplementary material to Horváth et al. [1]. It provides insights into the transformation rules between SysML [2] and Gamma [3], both on the conceptual (Section 1, Section 2) and the technical level (Section 3).

1 SysML to Gamma transformations

Figure 1: Composite Block transformation process [1].

^{*}IncQuery Labs cPlc., Budapest, Hungary. firstname.lastname@incquerylabs.com

[†]Johannes Kepler University Linz, Linz, Austria

[‡]Department of Measurement and Information Systems, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary

[§]Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, USA

[¶]TMT International Observatory LLC, Pasadena, CA, USA

“Figure 1 illustrates the transformation process of the SysML composite Block. Each Block of the composite system that has a State Machine as Classifier Behavior is transformed to a Gamma statechart. After the transformation of the individual Blocks, the Ports of the composite system are transformed, and the generated statecharts are connected to each other according to the system’s internal structure. Finally, the components are wrapped according to the compositional semantics of Gamma.” [1]

During the transformation, we build a traceability model, that contains a mapping between the source and target model to see which elements in the Gamma model were created from which elements in the SysML model. The traceability model is used in the transformation of the reachability property (Section 1.2) and the back-annotation (Section 2) phase.

The following sections give some details about the transformation and back-annotation processes.

Transformation of Blocks

First, the Ports of the Block are transformed to Interface Declarations and Port Definitions in Gamma with the corresponding Signal directions and Interface Realization Modes, i.e., requires, provides. Most elements are identically transformed, e.g., States, Transitions, Initial, Shallow/Deep History, and Choice Pseudostates. Block Value Properties (in SysML) are Variables (in Gamma) in the state machines. Time Event Triggers (in SysML) are Timeout Event References (in Gamma) on Transitions. JavaScript Guard Expressions and Action Statements are mapped to elements in Gamma Expression and Action Languages, respectively. To reflect the SysML semantics, bottom-up resolution strategy should be used for conflicting transitions in Gamma. Signal Events without Ports are transformed to Port Event Reference Triggers for each incoming Port because Signal Events are always bound to Ports in Gamma.

Transformation of Activity diagram actions

Activity Actions are transformed to JavaScript statements that are further translated to the Gamma Action Language. We chose this two-step translation because we restricted the user-written JavaScript code snippets so they could be translated to the Gamma Action and Expression languages. If we restrict the execution of Activities for a subset of Actions and Control Nodes to be reachable only via exactly one atomic, loop, and recursion-free, non-blocking Control Flow, then they can be expressed in the JavaScript subset we support. Besides, these Activities can be simulated in the design tools with the same semantics we apply in verification. Activities are traversed according to the Control Flow between the Initial and Activity Final Nodes. Local variables are generated from the Input and Output Pins of the Actions, which are bound according to the Data Flows in the Activity.

Read Self Actions are skipped during transformation because they would be redundant in Gamma, where the statecharts cannot refer to the variables of other statecharts. Read Structural Feature Actions are transformed to generated local variables, storing the value of the referred variable. Add Structural Feature Value Actions are transformed to assignment statements, whose left-hand side is the variable of the State Machine, and the right-hand side is a local variable providing the value from an earlier Action visited by the Control Flow.

Opaque Expressions in Value Specification Actions are transformed to generated local variable assignments with the JavaScript expression from the Action. Opaque Actions contain JavaScript statements. Incoming values of Input Pins are bound to local variables generated from Output Pins of other Actions. Named Input and Output Pins of the Opaque Action refer to variables in the Action. Send Signal Actions are transformed to syntactic `ALH.sendSignal` method calls that are translated to Raise Event Actions. `ALH.inState` is translated to State Reference Expressions.

Decision Nodes are transformed to if-else statements in JavaScript, which are transformed to non-deterministic Choices in Gamma. Actions on the outgoing Control Flow of a Merge Node are transformed and appended to the sequence of Actions transformed from each incoming Control Flow of the node.

Outgoing Control Flows of a Fork Node are transformed to sequential execution by appending the consecutive blocks of JavaScript statements in a fixed order, each block containing the transformed Actions of

```

package StatechartsPkg
import "interfaces.gcd"
@RegionSchedule = bottom-up
statechart GroundStation [
  port ExtControl: requires Control
  port Data: requires Data
  port SpControl: provides Control
  port Status: provides Status
] {
  var packets: integer := 0
  var forwardingEnabled: boolean := true
  transition from Receiving to Receiving when Data.Data
  transition from DataRegionInitial to Start
  transition from Idle to Operation when ExtControl.Start
  transition from Operation to Idle when ExtControl.Stop / raise
  SpControl.Stop
  transition from Start to Receiving when Data.Data
  transition from MainRegionInitial to Idle
  region Main {
    state Operation {
      region DataReception {
        state Start { entry / raise SpControl.Start; }
        state Receiving { entry / {
          var gen01: integer := packets + 1;
          packets := gen01;
          choice {
            branch [forwardingEnabled] {
              var gen02: integer := packets;
              raise Status.ReceivedPackets(gen02);
            }
            branch [!forwardingEnabled] {
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
    initial DataRegionInitial
  }
  state Idle
  initial MainRegionInitial
}
}

```

Listing 1: Ground Station State Machine in Gamma.

the respective Control Flow. Once all outgoing Control Flow chains are transformed, the transformation continues with Actions following the corresponding Join Node of the Fork Node.

After the whole Activity is traversed, the JavaScript snippets are merged into one script that is transformed to the Gamma Action Language.

Listing 1 depicts the Ground Station of the running example (see Figure 2 in [1]) in Gamma. The

RegionSchedule annotation of the statechart shows the bottom-up conflict resolution of the transitions. The Ports and their Realization Modes are declared in the header of the statechart. In the statechart body, the Variables of the statechart, the Transitions (with source and target States, Triggers, and Actions), and finally the Regions with States are listed. The **Start** and **Receiving** States contain the Gamma Entry Actions that resulted from the JavaScript and Activity transformations, respectively.

1.1 Component composition

Gamma supports several semantics for composing communicating statecharts. (1) The asynchronous-reactive semantics of Gamma is the most similar to the concurrent execution of State Machines in SysML [2]. In this execution semantics, statecharts run concurrently and react to events independently. Each statechart has a message queue from which it consumes messages. The message delivery is assumed to be reliable and non-blocking, but reading a message from an empty queue is blocking [4]. This execution mode has large performance implications due to many interleavings between the independently running components. (2) In the synchronous semantics, the components are controlled by the execution cycle of clocks limiting concurrency, which reduces the state space and may offer faster verification times (see Table 2 in [4]).

To reach scalability in terms of the model size and verification time for industrial models, we chose hybrid compositional semantics. The synchronous statecharts of the composite system are connected via channels and placed in a Synchronous Composite Component wrapped by an asynchronous adapter. Due to the adapter, the composite system operates asynchronously with the environment, while its internal behavior remains synchronous.

```

package CompositeSystemPkg
import "statecharts.gcd"
import "interfaces.gcd"
adapter SystemAsyncAdapter of component System : System {
  when any / run
  queue MQ (priority = 0, capacity = 1) {
    Control.any, Status.any
  }
}
sync System [
  port Control : requires Control
  port Status : provides Status
] {
  component station : GroundStation
  component spacecraft : Spacecraft
  bind Status -> station.Status
  bind Control -> station.ExtControl
  channel [ spacecraft.Data ] -o)- [ station.Data ]
  channel [ station.SpControl ] -o)- [ spacecraft.Control ]
}

```

Listing 2: The composite System in Gamma.

Listing 2 depicts the composite system of the running example in Gamma. The asynchronous adapter (**SystemAsyncAdapter**) has a message queue with capacity one, and its execution is triggered by an Event that arrives via any of its Ports (**Control**, **Status**). During execution, a message is removed from the head of the queue, converted to a Signal, and sent to the respective Port of the internal **GroundStation** statechart.

1.2 Transformation of the reachability property

The reachability property model in SysML is transformed to a Property model in the Gamma framework. The Gamma Property Model (GPM) supports the construction of formal expressions, similarly to the Computation Tree Logic (CTL) language [5]. Relying on the traceability model, Lifelines of the sequence diagram are transformed to Component Instance References for the corresponding statecharts, and State Invariants are translated to Path Formulas with exists future (EF) quantifier in GPM.

Listing 3 illustrates the reachability property of the running example in Gamma. The State and Variable References can be seen with their fully-qualified names, containing the name of the owner statecharts and Regions as well. Since the conditions in the reachability property must be fulfilled simultaneously, the expressions in GPM are connected with the logical AND operator.

```
import "CompositeSystemPkg"
component System
EF [(state spacecraft.TransmissionRegion.Sending)]
  && [variable spacecraft.battery < 80]
  && [(state station.DataReception.Receiving)]
  && [variable station.packets > 20]
```

Listing 3: The GPM model created from the reachability property.

2 Back-annotation of the Execution Trace

“If the reachability property is satisfied, Gamma returns an Execution Trace (Figure 2a) leading to the target state configuration. Each step of the trace contains: (1) the active state configuration of components including the values of variables (represented by a hexagon), (2) the set of input signals that were received by the composite system (represented by incoming arrows), (3) the set of output signals that were sent by the system (represented by outgoing arrows), and (4) the time that is spent before proceeding to the next step (in case of a timed system, represented by `wait X ms`).” [1]

On the SysML sequence diagram (Figure 2b), each component (Block) of the composite system and the incoming and outgoing Ports of the system are represented by individual Lifelines. The parameterized Signals sent between the Ports and the corresponding components are represented by asynchronous Messages between the Lifelines. Since the Execution Trace treats the composite system as a black-box, therefore the Messages sent between the components are hidden. Only the Messages sent between the Ports of the composite system, and the components are represented in the trace. The active state configuration of the Block’s State Machine is represented by State Invariants that can either refer to States or variables of the State Machine. The elapsed time between two steps of the Execution Trace is represented by Duration Constraints.

“Using the traceability model created during the forward transformation, we back-annotated the Execution Trace to a SysML sequence diagram, as depicted in Figure 2 for the running example in the paper. On the diagram, we can see that the composite system is in the initial state configuration when it receives a `Start` Signal via the `Control` Port and 1 ms elapses until we get to the next state configuration. After that, due to space limitations, we only represent the last state configuration of the trace. The `spacecraft` is in the `Transmitting` State, it has sent 20 packets to the `station` and its `battery` is 79. The `station` is in the `Receiving` state, it has received 20 packets and as a last action, it sends the `ReceivedPackets(20)` message via the `Status` Port of the composite system. Reaching the last state configuration proves that the reachability property of the running example is satisfied.” [1]

(a) Execution Trace in Gamma.

(b) SysML sequence diagram trace.

Figure 2: Execution Trace to sequence diagram mapping [1].

3 Technical realization

To implement the aforementioned transformation rules between the SysML and Gamma languages, we used the Viatra model query and transformation framework [6]. In Viatra, a model transformation consists of a *model query* and a *transformation action*. A *model query* is a declarative graph pattern that is evaluated on the source model to search for the prescribed constructs in it.

```

1 pattern stateMachineToplevelRegion(reg : Region, stateMachine : StateMachine) {
2   StateMachine.region(stateMachine, reg);
3 }

```

Listing 4: Top-level Region query in VQL.

Listing 4 shows an example model query written in the Viatra Query Language (VQL). The query looks for the topmost (top-level) Region of the SysML State Machine. If the Region is found, then it will be bound

to the `reg` pattern parameter, and the State Machine will be bound to the `stateMachine` parameter.

```
1 ruleFactory.createRule(StateMachineToplevelRegion.instance()).name("Top-level Region
  rule").action(match -> {
2   ModelObject mdRegion = (ModelObject) match.get("reg");
3   String name = getOrGenerateName(mdRegion);
4
5   Region gammaRegion = STATECHART_PKG.createRegion();
6   gammaRegion.setName(name);
7   gammaStatechart.getRegions().add(gammaRegion);
8   traceability.addTrace(mdRegion, gammaRegion);
9 }).build();
```

Listing 5: Top-level Region model transformation rule in VTL.

Listing 5 shows an example model transformation rule written in the Viatra Transformation Language (VTL). We used a `ruleFactory` to create the transformation rule. The rule uses the model query depicted in Listing 4 to find the top-level Region that will be transformed. If a pattern match is found, then the *transformation action* is executed. In the *action*, we read the `reg` parameter of the pattern to get the Region, and then we read its name or generate one for it. After that, we create a Region in Gamma with the same name and add the Region to the already created `gammaStatechart`. (Before the rule is executed, it is checked that `gammaStatechart` is the statechart that was created from the SysML `stateMachine`. The corresponding piece of code is not shown due to brevity.) Finally, we create a traceability link between the SysML Region (`mdRegion`) and the recently created Gamma Region (`gammaRegion`).

In this work, altogether, we implemented 92 model transformation rules between the SysML and Gamma languages.

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